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Review Article

**REVIEW ON: PATHOPHYSIOLOGY OF ARTHRITIS AND
DRUGS USED IN THE MANAGEMENT OF ARTHRITIS****Anisha A Kohale¹, Priya N Kothari¹, Anuj A Deshmukh², Amol V Sawale³, Kiran L
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Article Received: October 2022 **Accepted:** November 2022 **Published:** November 2022**Abstract:**

Arthritis is a chronic inflammation in joints, which mostly affects the bones. In the global prevalence of joint inflammation, it's means to be taken it as potential issues. Current treatments mostly targeting the inflammatory cytokines or effector molecules and oxidative stress involved in arthritis as pain relief temporarily. This review has mechanistically demonstrated the type of joint inflammation insights in to arthritis, such as osteoarthritis, gouty arthritis and rheumatoid arthritis to understand the clear background. This review has also highlighted the prevalence, mechanism and mediations used for arthritis, in which various causative agents are used to induce arthritis in preclinical studies that has been collectively elucidated. This review is first to be reported the mechanism of various arthritis causative agents. It pointed out the side effects of clinical medicine used for arthritis and suggested the natural products involved in medication for above-listed conditions. As comparatively natural products are low cost, easily available and beneficial than modern medicines with minimal side effects.

Keywords: Joint Inflammation, osteoarthritis, gouty arthritis, rheumatoid arthritis, natural therapeutics.**Corresponding author:****Anisha A Kohale,**Vidyabharti college of Pharmacy, Naidu Marg Camp,
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INTRODUCTION:

Arthritis is an inflammation in joints; this term includes over 100 disorders related to the bones and its joints. It is associated with the joint in fingers, hips, wrists and knees^[1]. The rate of this condition is increasing due to lifestyles and prominent to the aged people. Thus 1 out of 5 mankind was found to be in this disease. It can be caused due to age, genes, gender, injuries in joints and obesity. Some of the rare types of arthritis inflammation can be seen in organs, connective tissues and skins^[2]. To overcome this condition as a primary defense the medications such as acetophenone, Nonsteroidal Antiinflammatory Drugs (NSAIDs), corticosteroids and anti-rheumatic agents are prescribing for temporary relief as well these agents reported to have various side effects^[3-5]. Therapeutics to get rid of joint inflammation with minimal or no side effects are to be discovered. Few standard organizations have proved that many countries have been following their ancient traditional ways as natural therapeutics

and treating many diseases including joint inflammation^[6]. Natural therapeutics of preclinical experiments on various joint inflammation conditions such as osteoarthritis, gouty and rheumatoid arthritis have also been discussed in this review. In summary, fig. 1 describing the overview of joint inflammation clinical indications and their treatments. In brief, the occurrence of joint inflammation leading to cartilage destruction and synovium stimulation. As well, oxidative stress and inflammatory system are playing a significant role in this condition by activating T cells and inflammatory mediators such as cytokines and chemokines. Several medications are prescribed to inhibit T cell and oxidative stress from reducing inflammation. However, prolonged exposure leads to adverse effects, so present research on reducing inflammation without side effects with natural products is studying preclinically. This is the review of various agents to induce joint inflammation and protocol and mechanism collectively in preclinical studies and natural remedies against it.

Fig. 1: Overview of joint inflammation clinical indications and its treatments

Osteoarthritis:

Osteoarthritis is generally an articular cartilage disease found in articulation organ systems like a capsule, ligaments, menisci, periarticular muscle and synovium^[7]. Joint in our body can be classified into patellofemoral and tibiofemoral, where osteoarthritis occurs either of this joint, but most of the research has been studied in the patellofemoral joint because it is highly observed^[8]. It causes joint inflammation,

changes in cartilage structure and alters the anti-inflammatory and pro-inflammatory mechanisms^[9]. The risk factors include age, weight,

Prevalence:

gender, muscle weakness, obesity and repetitive movement of joints leads to trauma^[10]. The disease such as cancer, cardiovascular disease and diabetes are also associated with osteoarthritis.

Fig. 2. Osteoarthritis

A recent study has been reported that the National Health Interview Survey appraised approximately 1.4 crore people in the United States of America who were found to have an osteoarthritis symptom. Where 0.7 crore of the affected people seemed to be less than 65 y^[11]. In Greece, it was found that the prevalence rose up to 6 %. In osteoarthritis, women are more prominent than man where prevalence has raised from 3.7 % to 26.7 % around the globe^[10]. Prevalence in India has reported that the rate of osteoarthritis raised to 39 %, where 45 % of the women in India have this symptom over 65 y of age^[12]. The Johnston country osteoarthritis project has reported that the African-American population and the other people such as Irish, Italian, Lebanese, German, Moroccan and Asian have an osteoarthritis prevalence of 28 %^[13].

Mechanism:

In a normal joint, the bones are enclosed or covered by cartilage shielded by capsules associated with a synovial membrane that generates synovium^[14]. The integration of the capsule and synovium protects the cartilage and connective tissues in the bone. In case of aged or aberrant mechanical force that induce a chondrocyte from a lower metabolic activity which stimulates inflammatory mediators that produce macrophages during inflammation which includes cytokines and chemokines like Interleukins (IL) such as IL-1, IL-6, IL-8, IL-17 and IL-18, Monocyte Chemoattractant Protein 1 (MCP-1), Differentiation-Inducing Factor (DIA), growth-related oncogene and onco-statin-M will also generate Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS) such as Nitric oxide (NO), Oxygen (O₂), Hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) and Peroxynitrite (ONOO-)^[15]. In addition, lipid inflammatory mediators like Prostaglandin (PG) and Leukotrienes (LT) rise due to the chondrocyte metabolism that leads to the release of proteolytic enzymes that alters the normal structural formation of joints by increasing the synovium and fragmentation of

cartilage that lead to pain and immobility in osteoarthritis condition^[16].

Medication for osteoarthritis:

The first line of medication prescribing for osteoarthritis is acetaminophen, which is also known as paracetamol; at a mild stage due to its antipyretic and analgesic properties^[17]. The mechanism of this drug against osteoarthritis is yet to be studied. Due to the absence of anti-inflammatory activity and also it causes hepatotoxicity^[18]. NSAIDs such as diclofenac, celecoxib, ibuprofen, ketoprofen and naproxen were used to prescribe. The NSAID mechanism against osteoarthritis is to inhibit the prostaglandin isoenzymes like Cyclooxygenase 1 (COX1) and COX2 where COX1 inhibition causes gastro-toxicity so COX2 selective NSAID were used. COX2 enzyme are used to be highly expressed in inflammation conditions^[19]. NSAIDs have analgesic, antipyretic and anti-inflammatory activity with the COX2 inhibition ability which is used against osteoarthritis. Even though NSAIDs reduce the osteoarthritis inflammation, it is not advisable to take due to its severe side-effects like hepatotoxicity, renal-toxicity, gastrointestinal-toxicity and cardiovascular disorders consuming for long term or on overdose^[20]. Corticosteroids also suggested for the treatment of osteoarthritis because of its immunosuppressive and anti-inflammatory properties. Betamethasone, dexamethasone, methylprednisolone and triamcinolone were used for the treatment. The mechanism is to act on steroid hormone receptor to inhibit the inflammation by the reduction of microvascular permeability to prevent the inflammatory cells from accumulation and stimulation of neutrophils to inhibit the production of PG and LT^[21,22]. Certain research has reported that corticosteroids have many side effects, such as skin disease, cushing syndrome, ophthalmologic, cardiovascular disease, neurotoxicity, gastro toxicity and poor growth^[23]. In addition, opioid analgesics like tramadol and oxycodone were commonly used

for treating osteoarthritis. When the patient takes opioid analgesics, it binds with the opioid receptor in the central and peripheral nervous system, which inhibits the nociceptive pathway of pain^[24]. This medication also shows the side effect, for example, gastrointestinal diseases, skin diseases, neurotoxicity and autonomic nervous system disorder^[25].

GOUTY ARTHRITIS:

Gouty arthritis is a disorder called as unwalkable disease where the uric acid level in the serum seems to be increased in this condition^[26]. Gout is a type of arthritis that causes inflammation in joints of the toe, elbow, ankles, fingers and knees with indications of tender, hot, red and swollen in joints. Which is due to

the diet, heredity combinations and raised level of urate in serum^[27]. Risk factors that cause gout are age (40- 50 y), medications (such as aspirin, levodopa, niacin, etc.) alcohol intake, lead exposure, obesity, high blood pressure, diabetes, hypothyroidism, hypertension, cancer and kidney diseases^[28,29]. There are some diseases associated with gout are type-2 diabetes, hyperuricemia, hypertension and Cardiovascular Disease (CVD)^[30]. Reasons behind the gout increase are the lacking of common habits like diet, exercises, obesity and metabolic syndromes such as cardiovascular disease, diabetes and ischemic stroke^[31].

Fig. 3. Gouty Arthritis.

Prevalence:

A recent study has reported that 4-6 % of men and approximately 2 % of women are affected by gouty arthritis in western countries such as Europe, United States, Canada, Australia and England. Commonly it occurs 1-3 % of the common people and men are more frequently affected than women. It is evident from the recent literature which an increase in prevalence in that the percentage exceeded up to 10 % for males and 6 % for females in many countries^[32]. Other countries like Germany, USA, Europe, Switzer land, Australia, Israel, South Korea, Japan and Canada it ranges from 6 % to 10 %. This is because of less diet, food habitat, obesity due to no utilization of exercises and syndrome X^[33].

Mechanism:

Gouty arthritis can be caused by various factors where the mechanism is when the uric acid level in our blood increased due to the obesity of other factors that is need to be filtered and excreted through the kidney by the enzyme called uricase^[34]. The excess level of uric acid in the blood cannot be completely excreted; in that case, the uric acid further increases

and settles in renal tissues and joints and later forms a crystal called uric acid. That crystal interacts with the phagocytic cells and induces pro-inflammatory cytokines release, which will release macrophages^[35]. Microcrystal infiltration in synovial membrane will also induce leukocytes to lyse the lysosomal membrane and oozed out of lysosomal enzymes into the blood. PG and LT get raised and lead to the formation of ROS^[35].

Rheumatoid arthritis:

Rheumatoid arthritis is a disease associated with joints commonly called an autoimmune inflammatory disease that leads to structural changes in multiple joints where the feet and hand joints are the first affected part and later other parts of the body are affected, resulting in severe pain and immobility^[36]. As a result of structural changes in joints it causes erosions in bone and degradation of cartilage^[37]. This induces macrophages and neutrophils to release cytokines like IL-1 β , IL-6, IL-17 and TNF- α , leading to the destruction of joints' pleiotropic traits rheumatoid arthritis^[38]. It also causes the reduction of red blood cells in the blood, inflammation in the

lungs and heart^[39]. Common factors causing rheumatoid arthritis are age, sex, race, poverty, chain-smoking, alcohol consumption and obesity, where the

diseases associate with rheumatoid arthritis are CVD, atrial fibrillation, stroke and autoimmune diseases^[40,41]

Fig. 4. Rheumatoid Arthritis

Prevalence:

The report of the Rochester Epidemiology Project has said that the prevalence rate of rheumatoid arthritis has increased from 4 % to 5.3 % in the United States. Where also, among the 1 million people, 531 women and 277 men are affected by this disorder. People above 65 y old are more prominent than the adults, where 894 aged people are affected in 1 million population^[42]. The rate of rheumatoid prevalence is increasing every year of 2.5 % of women and 2 % of men. Other countries like Denmark, Finland, Sweden and Norway the prevalence rate of rheumatoid arthritis has been increased from 200 to 500 people in 1 million population^[43,44]. In addition, the Global Burden of the disease has also reported that the prevalence of rheumatoid arthritis that been increased from 0.5 % to 1.1 % globally. In Southern European countries, the prevalence rate increases from 0.3 % to 0.7 % and in many developing countries, prevalence is not exact but approximately increased from 0.1 % to 0.5 % reported by the American College of rheumatology^[45].

Mechanism:

The people with rheumatoid arthritis seem to have an increased C-Reactive Peptide (CRP) in the. Anticitrul blood^[46]linated-Protein Antibodies (ACPA) and Peptidyl-Arginine-Deiminase (PAD) enzyme are responsible for causing rheumatoid arthritis. Among that ACPA, it is associated with the genetics where abnormal antibody glycosylation can be found in rheumatoid arthritis condition that induces the inflammation in joints^[47]. During inflammation, activated T-lymphocytes enter into synovium, leading

to aggregation of CD4 and infiltration of CD8 cells. These induce the dendritic cells by major histocompatibility complex-2 molecules expression, which stimulates the immune response in the joint tissues^[48,49]. This leads to thickening of the synovium, erosion of cartilage, the disintegration of bone and joint. The TRANCE receptor induces the production of osteoclast in the inflammation responsible for joint degradation. TNF- α is a major factor in rheumatoid arthritis where it is released when rheumatoid factor (ACPA) is formed were also TNF is stimulated by IL-17 in the hypersensitivity condition^[50]. The role of PAD is to convert arginine to citrulline where type 4 PAD inhibition was encoded by a gene called PADI-4 which is also responsible for the rheumatoid arthritis^[51].

Medication for rheumatoid arthritis:

NSAIDs like ibuprofen and naproxen are used to treat rheumatoid arthritis due to its anti-inflammatory and analgesic properties. Mechanisms of NSAIDs against rheumatoid arthritis have the ability to prevent the PG production and mainly inhibition of COX^[52]. Even though it has anti-inflammatory activities, it is not advisable to take due to its severe side effects such as gastrointestinal bleeding, high blood pressure, antihypertensive, renal toxicity, hepatotoxicity and . Corticosteroids like prednisone, triamcinolone and dexamethasone were used to reduce the joints pain. Cortisol is a hormone produced in our body in the adrenal gland where the role corticosteroids is to reduce the immune response that results in an inflammation reduction^[53]. In addition, steroid

hormones are administrated to reduce rheumatoid arthritis that acts as immune-modulators to suppress the formation of antibodies during inflammation. Immune modulators are the inhibitors of the immune system^[54]. Where corticosteroids are also not advisable to take due to its major side effects like vaso constrictive effects, asthma, nausea, pulmonary edema and autoimmune diseases were also causes Sjogren syndrome, graves ophthalmopathy and osteoarthritis while consuming long – term^[55]. Disease-Modifying Antirheumatic Drugs (DMARDs) like methotrexate, leflunomide, hydroxychloroquine and sulfasalazine were used to treat rheumatoid arthritis. The mechanism of DMARD is to initiate the adenosine hormone to neutrophil reduction, LTB4 inhibition produced by neutrophils^[56]. It also reduces the level of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as IL-1, IL-6, IL-8 and inhibited the collagenase expression in synovium to terminate inflammation in

joints^[57]. In addition, it inhibits autoimmune responses like malfunction of lymphocytes, T-cell activation and B-cell activators^[58]. DMARD are powerful drugs it causes side effects like stomach upset, gastro-toxicity, bone marrow erosion, lung disease, hepatotoxicity, neurotoxicity and liver disease^[59], so it's better to stop consuming this drug.

Natural products:

World Health Organization (WHO) has been reported that 75 % of people in global of developing countries are dependent on ancient traditional medicines like Ayurveda, Ebers Papyrus, Hippocrates and Chinese herbal medicine. These medicines have been followed as more than 1000 y due to its beneficial role and treatment against diverse disorders in humans and animals^[60,61]

TABLE 1: ANTIARTHRITIC ACTIVITY OF NATURAL THERAPEUTICS ON OSTEOARTHRITIS AT CLINICAL/ PRECLINICAL STUDIES

Therapeutics	Source	Formulation	Causative agent/Model	Therapeutic effects	Reference
Honokiol	Magnolia officinalis	Aqueous solution	NA/Patients	Inhibition of COX2, PGE2 and IL Signalling	[62]
Curcumin	Etlingera elatior	Curcuminin aqueous phosphatidycholine	NA/Patients	Protects the degradation of chondrocytes and proteoglycan and prevents (AP)-1, IL-1 β and NF-K	[63]
SKI-306X	Clematis mandshurica; Prunella vulgaris; Trichosanthes kirilowii	Aqueous with the ratio of 1:2:1	Collagenas/ Rabbit	Inhibited proteoglycan degradation, glycosaminoglycan releases and structural changes in cartilage	[64]
Carbopol,aerosol, veegum and charcoal	Mud of Lake of Urmia in Iran	Ointment	NA/Patients	Pain relieved and decreased hs-CRP and TNF- α	[65]

Epigallocatechin-3-gallate, gallic acid, agallin and methylxanthines	Camelliasinensis	Aqueous solution	NA/Patients	Inhibited leukocytes, myeloperoxidase, chondrocyte and ROS, protects DNA damage and restores cartilage	[66]
Naringin	Skimmiajaponica	Aqueous solution	Surgical/ Rats	Decreased IL-1 β , TNF- α , matrix-metalloproteinase-13, free radicals (NO) and ADAMTS-5 antibody	[67]
Alpha-mangostinis	Garcinia mangostana	Aqueous solution	IL-1 β /Rats	Prevents NO, PG-E2, COX2 and metalloproteinase s-(3,9 and 13) as well inhibited NF-kB and p65 nuclear translocation pathways	[68]
Aucubin	Aucuba japonica	Aqueous solution	NA/Patients	Prevents NO, COX2 and metalloproteinase s-(3,9 and 13) as well inhibited p65 nuclear translocation pathway	[69,70]
Anemonin	Ranunculus eschscholtzii	Aqueous solution	Surgical/ Mouse	Cartilage regeneration and decreases metalloproteinase-13, ADAMTS-5, PG and collagen X as well inhibited NF-KB pathway	[71]
Salvianolic acid-Bis	Salvia miltiorrhiza	Intraperitoneal saline solution	MIA/Mouse	Inhibits NO, COX2, metalloproteinase s-13 and ADAMTS5 and suppressed NK-KB and P65 nuclear translocation pathways	[72]

TABLE 2 ANTIARTHRITIC: ACTIVITY OF NATURAL THERAPEUTICS ON GOUTY ARTHRITIS AT CLINICAL/ PRECLINICAL STUDIES

Therapeutics	Source	Formulation	Causative agent/Model	Therapeutic effects	Reference
Curcuminoids	Curcuma longa	Aqueous solution	MSU/Mice	Reduces paw edema, normalizes lipid peroxidation and renal markers. Inhibited cytokines, purine metabolism and enhances xanthine oxidase inhibitor	[73]
Leaves	Pistacia Integerrima	Aqueous leaf extract	Fructose/Mice	Reduced uric acid level and promoted antioxidants as well inhibits xanthine oxidase	[74]
Leaves	Sparattosperma leucanthum	Ethyl acetate/methyl/aqueous leaf extract	MSU/Mice	Protects synovial cells damage, inhibits xanthine oxidase and reduces uric acid level	[75]
Leaves/ α and B Amyrins	Tabebuia roseoalba	Ethanollic leaves extract	MSU/Rats	Reduces uric acid level, paw volume, IL-1, IL-6, IL-8 and TNF- α . Suppressed NF-KB and COX2 pathway	[76]
Flower head	Helianthus annuus	Aqueous extract of head powder	MSU/Rats	Reduces Paw edema, IL-10 and restored cartilage, synovium deformation and cell infiltration	[77]
Piperine	Piper nigrum	Aqueous solution	MSU/Rats	Restores the level of uric acid, lipid peroxidation, lysosomal enzymes and TNF- α	[78]
Root powder	Withania somnifera	Gum acacia with root powder	MSU/Rats	Reduces the paw inflammation, lipid peroxidation, lysosomal enzymes and cytokines	[79]
Triphala	Emblica officinalis Terminalia chebula; Terminalia belliricain the ratio of 1:1:1	Aqueous solution	MSU/Rats	Reduces the paw edema, lipid peroxidation, lysosomal enzymes and TNF- α as well cartilage regeneration	[80]
Quercetin	Beverages vegetables and fruits	Aqueous solution	MSU/Rats	Reduces lysosomal enzymes and lipid peroxidation in joints tissues. Also, inhibited COX2, IL-1 β , TNF- α , PGE2 and NO and restored leukocyte infiltration in joints	[81]
Seed powder	Cyamopsis tetragonoloba	Aqueous seed extract	MSU/Rats	Reduces renal markers and oxidative stress in spleen and joint homogenate. Importantly, protects bone erosion in articular cartilage	[82]

TABLE 3: ACTIVITY OF NATURAL THERAPEUTICS ON RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS ANTIARTHRITIC AT CLINICAL/PRECLINICAL STUDIE

Therapeutics	Source	Formulation	Causative agent/Model	Therapeutic effects	Reference
Root	Withania somnifera	Aqueous root extract	Collagen and adjuvant/Rats	Reduces ankylosis, lipid peroxidation, glycoprotein and cartilage regeneration	[83,84]
Rutin	Eucalyptus tereticornis	Aqueous solution	Adjuvant/Rats	Reduces joint erosion, cartilage degradation, TNF- α and IL-1 β in NF-KB pathway	[85]
Total flavonoids	Astragalus propinquus	Aqueous solution	Adjuvant/Rats	Reduces joint swelling and arthritic index, restored BAX and BCL-2 and inhibited PGE2, NF-KB and osteoprotegerin	[86]
Root	Tripterygium wilfordii	Aqueous root extract	Collagen/Mice	Reduces joint swelling, arthritic score and antibody titers and restored cartilage destruction	[87]
Leaves	Calotropis procera	Methanol leaf extract	Adjuvant/Rats	Increases antioxidants, decreases PGE2, TNF- α and lipid peroxidation and cartilage regeneration	[88]
Tamarixinin-A	Tamaricaceae	Aqueous solution	Collagen and Adjuvant/Rats	Restores synovium hyperplasia, bone erosion and cartilage degradation, decreases TNF- α , IL-6 and IL1- β and inhibited p38 and NF-KB pathway	[89]
Leaves	Ziziphora clinopodioides	Aqueous leaf extract	Xylene and carrageenan/Rats	Reduces paw volume, pannus formation and cartilage joint erosion and inhibited autacoids	[90]
Seeds	Abrus precatorius seed	Ethanol extract	Adjuvant/Rats	Prevents pannus formation, joint inflammation and cartilage degradation and inhibits cytokines and the COX2 pathway	[91]
Leaves	Baccharis genistelloides	Aqueous leaves extract	Collagen/Rats	Prevents antigen presenting cells, decreases cytokines, DNA damage and articular cartilage degradation	[92]
Bark	Semecarpus anacardium	Aqueous bark extract	Adjuvant/Rats	Reduces lipid peroxidation, macrophages, cytokines and restores joint damages	[93]

CONCLUSION:

Traditional medicine or natural therapeutics has been proved their potential antiarthritic activities to recover joint inflammation in various clinical and preclinical studies. Natural products and its active compounds are found to have significant activity

when compared with chemical medications with no side effects. Our review has collectively covered the various factors/ agents causing or to induce joint inflammation such as osteoarthritis, gouty and rheumatoid arthritis. The chemicals that are used to cause arthritis and their mode of action have been

discussed based on the report presented by researchers. Various researches have suggested that the natural product is beneficial compounds which treat arthritis without any side effects in preclinical studies. Many of the natural products with the essential ability against arthritis were not yet experimented and trails, which can be further study to understand its clear therapeutic mechanism against arthritis. This could be studied through *in vivo*, *in silico* and *in vitro* approaches.

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